

Research Article

The Application of Ethics in The Development of Cyber-Physical System

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Abstract: *This article discusses the application of ethics in the development of cyber-physical systems. The impact of the development of cyber-physical systems has become a debate between philosophers and technologists today. This is because cyber-physical system technology has changed the thinking and landscape of modern society. This issue clearly has an impact on human relationships because humans are becoming more dependent and influential with the development of technology. This makes human values fade into themselves until they are completely dependent on technology. Humans will be distracted by technology until they forget about the real reality of human life, to the point of causing various mental illness problems such as depression, anxiety, and bipolar. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to discuss the development of cyber-physical systems that threaten the ethical values of society. Meanwhile, the objective of our study is to identify the influence of cyber-physical systems on ethical values in society and the challenges to the development of cyber-physical systems. This study uses the literature review method. This method is used to find accurate information in online databases and has credibility because most of the review articles are based on previous studies produced from 2017 to 2021 to see the difference of opinion between philosophers and technologists. According to the analysis of this article, numerous studies have been conducted to examine ethical changes in the development of cyber-physical systems. Researchers are taking this issue seriously and doing a thorough analysis of the changes in ethical values that are impacted by the advancement of cyber-physical systems due to this change in ethics.*

Keywords: *cyber-physical system, CPS, ethics, cyber ethics, development*

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1. INTRODUCTION

A new digitally networked embedded systems, known as “cyber-physical systems” (CPS), link the physical and digital worlds through sensors and actuators (Esterle & Grosu, 2016). The term “CPS” was first used in 2006 by Helen Gill of the US National Science Foundation (NSF). Since then, the system that connects the offline and online worlds has come to be called ‘CPS’ (Lee, 2015). Since then, the NSF has generously funded his studies on CPS (Shi et al., 2011). This is because it can have significant social, environmental, and economic impacts. Cyber-physical systems (CPS), a class of large-scale, interconnected systems composed of physical and computational elements, are currently of interest to academia, industry, and government (Xu et al., 2014; Gürdür et al., 2016). With the advent of Industry

4.0 and the Internet of Things (IoT), embedded systems have given way to CPSs in the manufacturing sector. By integrating cutting-edge capabilities through IoT and the Web of Things, enabling the connection of physical reality operations with computing and communication infrastructure, CPS is an excellent foundation for the development of advanced industrial systems and applications. (Xu et al., 2018; Lu 2017). Cyber-physical system "CPS" is a new generation digital system consisting of two main functional components such as intelligent data management, analysis, and computing power to create cyberspace and advanced connectivity to ensure real-time data collection from the physical world and information feedback from cyberspace (Lee et al., 2015). Connected CPS may be widely deployed in the coming decades to solve global needs in sectors such as energy, water, healthcare, and transportation (Satchidanandan & Kumar, 2016). This study is an overview of the literature on the theoretical foundations and applications of CPS. Due to their potential to have significant social, environmental, and economic impacts, CPS are currently of interest to scientists, businesses, and governments. According to several recent studies (Li et al., 2018; Lu 2017b; Xu & Duan, 2018), CPS has become a central part of 'Industry 4.0'. CPS aims to accelerate the deployment of large-scale systems by improving the adaptability, autonomy, efficiency, functionality, reliability, security, and availability of these systems. CPS applications cover many fields such as agriculture, energy, medical, industrial, transportation and smart environment. A few studies reveal the current state of Cyber Physical System research.

However, there is no thorough and systematic review of research on the application of ethics in the design of cyber-physical systems. This journal comprehensively discusses the definition, theoretical foundations, ethical applications, and applications of CPS. Next, the current state of his CPS applied research on ethical management of CPS is discussed. This journal examines the ethical concerns surrounding cyber-physical human systems (CPHS). Intelligent cyber-physical systems (CPS) are emerging due to the increasing integration of computers, communications, and controls into various physical systems with sensors and actuators and increasing levels of automation enabled by machine learning and artificial intelligence. being developed. The increasing use of such technologies in dynamic public environments is changing the way people interact with intelligent CPSs. The development of smart and connected cars, robotics in manufacturing, robotic surgery, precision agriculture and other technologies, transportation, manufacturing, energy, and healthcare are all undergoing this dramatic change. Such developments are likely to continue and accelerate over the next few years and decades. Considerable ethical challenges are expected in the development of such a revolutionary CPHS that impacts both individuals and society. This article presents a structure for analysing how the emergence of cyber-physical systems threatens society's ethical norms. The purpose of our research is to elucidate how ethical ideals in society are affected by cyber-physical systems and what difficulties arise in their growth.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

For this literature review, we have taken various opinions and views done in previous studies related to our topic. We take information from various credible sources such as journal articles and additional sources such as information search results. Among the journal articles we use are "When Smart Systems Fail: The Ethics of Cyber-Physical Critical Infrastructure Risk (Grady et al., 2021)", "Applications of Cyber-Physical System: A Literature Review (Chen, 2017)", "Human Digital Shadow: Data-based Modeling of Users and Usage in the Internet of Production (Mertens et al., 2021)", "A Framework for Ethics in Cyber-Physical-Human Systems (Sampath & Khargonekar, 2020)", "Ethics Aspects of Embedded and Cyber-Physical Systems (Thekkilakattil & Dodig-Crnkovic, 2015)", and "Designing Ethical Cyber-Physical Industrial Systems (Trentesaux & Rault, 2017)".

2.1 Ethics

In today's technological development, ethics is very important to make sure in control something, so it does not exceed certain limits. Based on Merriam-Webster, an online dictionary, ethics may be described as a set of moral principles that include: a moral value theory or system. Ethics and Morals are different from each other. Ethics is a guide about what is good and what is bad to do, it can also help us for decision making or making judgement. However, morality is a system used to modify and regulate our behavior. This system can create a moral person who has a high sense of justice and a high sense of humanity towards others. According to Trentesaux and Rault (2017), ethics was initially a field of philosophy. Ethical behavior is in line with the culture that has to do with morality and justice (Morahan, 2015). Ethics has different types based on its use in various fields. According to Trentesaux and Rault (2017) have discussed techno/engineering ethics in the literature review section of their article. From the review made, they discovered that in industry, techno/engineering ethics has been addressed mostly in the fields of information and communication technology (ICT) and robotic engineering. It focuses heavily on cyber security, data usage ethics, young people and the internet, privacy, and other topics in ICT (Capurro, 2000), (Bhadauria et al., 2010). The research done by them is more directed to the field of robotic engineering. According to the authors, the presence of the IEEE-RAS Technical Committee (TC) on Roboethics aided in the realization of various initiatives that had an influence on Roboethics. The "Euron Roboethics Atelier" project in 2005 aimed to draw the first Roboethics Roadmap as a guide for those in this field, there are also other projects such as European Union (EU) Project Ethicbots (2005-2008) and EU Project RoboLaw (Palmerini et al., 2016). There are two ethical theories presented in the study made by (Alesgier, 2016), namely rule utilitarianism theory and social contract theory. The authors also found that the main factor that encourages the use of techno ethics by researchers is often related to the idea of a charter to be signed through the Hippocratic oath (an oath of ethics historically taken by physicians).

In addition, the author (Trentesaux & Rault, 2017) also discussed machine ethics, it has complexity level 2 to 4. At complexity level 2, AI can be dealt with well by identifying and verifying or limiting (proof) all behaviors and conditions different research object which is the designed system. The authors state in this regard that the traditional and historical technique is a holistic way to create autonomous systems utilized by industrial R&D engineers. At level 3, the legal responsibility of the learning entity from a lawyer's point of view can be addressed with a set of very innovative works, there is a large corpus of law that is only human-centered and has nothing to do with artificial beings. This suggests the emergence of a new species other than humans, and it may also mean that the human rights constitution should be revised correspondingly. For example, the study made by (Dreier & Döhmman, 2012) has discussed service robot administrative control organization and legal liability regime, as well as the question of service robot autonomy. In addition, the study made by (Sampath & Khargonekar, 2020) also discusses artificial intelligence ethics. Automation, artificial intelligence, and machine learning are being integrated into the next-generation cyber-physical human system (CPHS), a type of variation of cyber-physical system. The authors take and focus on the latest IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems (A/IS) study "Ethically Aligned Designed (EAD)" (IEEE, 2019). This study provides an ethical analysis conceptual framework based on three pillars: universal human values, political self-determination and data agency, and technical dependability. These three pillars serve as the foundation for general principles critical to the ethical design of A/IS, such as human rights, well-being, data agency, efficacy, openness, accountability, misuse awareness, and competence. Detailed ideas on how to deal with this ethics issue can be supplied, with the main purpose of assisting A/IS developers in reducing to practice applicable principles in the goods or services they supply.

There are examples of ethics that are practiced in certain fields to achieve their goals, it is also known as a code of ethics which is a guide for an organization. According to Sampath and Khargonekar (2020), in the United States, the National Society of Professional Engineers, a group specifically for

engineers, has a code of ethics for engineers that is organized for all professionals that work there. Engineers' services, according to this code of ethics, must be honest, unbiased, fair, and equitable, and must be committed to the preservation of public health, safety, and welfare. Furthermore, the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), a US-based worldwide learned society for computing, has a Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct that asserts that "the actions of computing professionals change the world.". To act responsibly they need to always think about the impact on society rather than thinking about their work alone, consistently to support the public good. The Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct expresses the conscience of the profession". According to Thekkilakattil and Dodig-Crnkovic (2015), the European Union (EU) has made a proposal related to robotics and artificial intelligence at the parliamentary level (Delvaux, 2016). Aside from presenting the fundamental goals of human safety, integrity, safety, autonomy, and dignity, the EU Parliament's goals are to unite and stimulate European innovation in robotics and artificial intelligence (AI). The ethical framework is made up of the Robotics Charter, which includes the Code of Ethical Conduct for Robotics Engineers, and Licenses for Designers and Users, which are based on the principles of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and are dependent on the establishment of the European Agency for Robotics and AI.

2.2 *Cyber-Physical System*

Cyber-physical system (CPS) is now a topic that is hotly discussed in various fields such as industry, academia and government because of its potential to impact society, the environment and the economy. The definition of CPS changes according to various perspectives in the scientific community. According to Hong Chen (2017) in his study, CPS is a physical and engineering system monitored, coordinated, controlled, and integrated by a computational and communication core. CPS is also a new generation of integrated systems with computational capabilities and physical capabilities that can interact with humans through various modalities or ways. The author concludes that CPS is a combination of embedded systems, real-time systems, distributed sensor systems, and controls that focus on the complex interdependence and integration between the cyber and physical worlds and are made up of tightly integrated computation, communication, control, and physical elements. Although CPS has been used since the early 1970s, when the first microprocessors appeared, it began to alter in 2006, when Dr Helen Gill from the United States National Science Foundation's Program on Cyber-Physical Systems invented the phrase "cyber-physical system" (RMIT University, 2019). Cyber-physical systems are classified into two types: autonomous cyber-physical systems and closed-loop human machine systems. Autonomous cyber-physical systems are systems that can make decisions and operate "stand-alone". However, nowadays, the development of many cyber-physical systems in semi-autonomous systems, for example, semi-autonomous drones, users can set the flight path and real-time machine vision to allow the drone to avoid obstacles, this can reduce the dependence on the need for manual flight. The system is a cognitive system, it can learn from the environment, from the human itself to make decisions in real-time, but it is not completely dependent on this system, humans remain part of the decision-making process in this system (Roberto, 2019).

Cyber-physical system (CPS) can be applied to various fields involving computing and technology. According to Sampath & Khargonekar (2020) who studied the computer-physical-human system (CPHS), CPS allows basic control system knowledge to be used and incorporated into new technological systems. Applications in fields such as manufacturing, energy, transportation, aerospace, and military are all examples of industries, it can also be applied to biomedical and healthcare fields and may be many more in the future. For example, an autonomous system that can control the driving of a vehicle that can decide what road to take. Industry 4.0 and smart manufacturing can also happen by applying CPS. The integration of renewable electricity from solar and wind turbines is key to a smart electric grid (Annaswamy & Amin, (2013) enabled with CPS. In addition, smart CPHS is an integrated combination of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI). CPHS with AI and ML is applied to e-commerce, information processing and computer vision. Smart electric grid, smart manufacturing

and smart health has become a topic for research and development, and we can expect a wider commercial development of smart CPHS in the future with the development of current technology. According to Chen (2017) taking from (Wang et al., 2007; Li et al., 2008, 2014; Tan et al., 2010), CPS applications include many fields and disciplines such as agriculture, energy, health care, manufacturing, transportation, and smart environment. CPS also deals with physical systems such as transportation, energy, medical, and defense. Based on the research done, The author discovered that CPS is also used in agriculture, education, energy management, environmental monitoring, intelligent transportation, medical devices and systems, process control, security, smart city and smart home, and smart manufacturing.

Cyber-physical system (CPS) also has various types according to the field to be applied such as the production field, according to Mertens et al., (2021) CPS is used for the internet of production, it is known as cyber-physical production systems (CPPS). Because of the system's complexity, data generation is frequently heterogeneous, unstructured, and isolated. The first step in realizing the goal of the Internet of Production should be the connectivity of machines, people, and whole production sites throughout the world to enable interaction and information exchange with one another. information about all available sensors and systems is stored in the Data Lake, it refers to a large-scale storage place to store raw data to handle a high amount of unstructured real-time data. The digital shadow aims are then to link abstract and aggregate data from the Data Lake for specific activities and concerns, allowing knowledge-based and real-time decision making in manufacturing, development, and related disciplines. The interdisciplinary group of authors is persuaded that an extra anthropocentric perspective in the form of a Human Digital Shadow has enormous promise for addressing current and future CPPS concerns in a more sustainable and integrated manner. Despite amazing development in the field of automation, humans will continue to be the primary and most significant function in socio-technical production systems in the long term. The Human Digital Shadow encompasses all data that can be provided to human actors in a sociotechnical system as a source or sink. The Human Digital Shadow is similar to the Digital Shadow, but it aids in the examination of actual connections between individuals, technology, and organizations. Human Digital Shadows can include, for example, their behavior and movement patterns. To study this concept, the authors used different perspectives to apply Human Digital Shadows in the CPPS that was developed based on a Delphi Study and then used SWOT to make an analysis. In addition, there are also CPS used for machine learning and intelligence such as (Sampath & Khargonekar, 2020) cyber-physical-human systems (CPHS). Continuous integration of control, communication, and computing into various types of physical systems using sensors and actuators, in conjunction with rising levels of automation, enables machine learning and artificial intelligence to produce a smart system known as smart CPS. The effect of this CPHS innovation affects individuals and society, especially ethical issues. The study conducted by the authors provides a framework to assess current and possible future ethical issues in smart CPHS. In recent years, the term CPHS has been used to capture the entire CPS interacting and embedded in human society (IFAC, 2018).

3. METHODOLOGY

Literature reviews are one of the methods used by researchers to obtain information from past studies conducted by other researchers that have topics related to or similar to the one you are studying. Literature reviews can provide an overview of the topic being studied to allow you to study your topic in more depth and provide a good understanding. One of the processes to get good literature reviews is to search, evaluate, identify, and write.

For search, researchers look for suitable materials to be used as literature reviews. Researchers look for it in online database platforms such as Science Direct, IEEE, Emerald Insight and Google Scholar. All of these are online databases that provide materials that are credible and mostly accurate. Researchers use the keywords "cyber-physical", "cyber-physical system", "ethic", and "development" to

find suitable material according to the topic under study. The researcher arranged the time of the article from 2017 to 2023 and set the category "journal article", to find information that is still relevant and accurate to the needs of this study. Researchers also use Boolean search techniques "AND", "OR" and "NOT" to find materials that are really related only to the topic under study. For example, "ethics" AND "cyber-physical system" AND "development". Search results with this search technique will produce materials that have those keywords and are related.

Next, evaluate. The researcher evaluates the material that has been searched for. A total of 15 journal articles were found by researchers that are related to the topic under study. After evaluating and appropriateness of the content reviewed in this journal article, the researcher decided to select 6 articles from the 15 articles because they fit the topic under study.

Next, identify. After the material was obtained and selected, the researcher began to read one by one the journal articles that were searched to identify what relevant content could be placed in the literature reviews. This looks at the relevance of the content to the topic being studied.

Finally, write. After identifying what content is appropriate. Researchers start writing literature reviews in the past tense because it is a past study. Content in the journal article will be read and paraphrased into its own sentences to avoid plagiarism.

Apart from searching for information in the online database, the researcher also used the search engine "Google Chrome" to find additional information to support or improve the written content.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 *Influences of the cyber-physical system towards society ethics values.*

A cyber-physical system (CPS) is a technical system that communicates with the physical world via networked computers, robots, and artificial intelligence. Other examples of CPS include smart grids, self-driving car systems, medical surveillance, industrial control systems, robotic systems, recycling, and autopilot avionics. Given that every type of system has advantages and disadvantages, developing human ethical standards should be given priority alongside the development of cyber-physical systems. To assist European legislators in foreseeing potential future issues associated with advancements in CPS, robots, and artificial intelligence, the Scientific and Technological Options Assessment Panel (STOA) has established a project titled "Ethical Aspects of CPS." Health care, agriculture and the provision of food, manufacturing, energy and essential infrastructure, logistics and transportation, and the safety and protection of human communities are among the subjects addressed by the CPS. The system should therefore emphasize a variety of elements, such as those pertaining to the social, technological, environmental, economic, political, ethical, and demographic aspects of CPS use. This is because the CPS could have an impact and result in issues down the road. As a result, the development of this CPS has made it possible for social scientists and technological specialists to collaborate on an in-depth investigation of probable CPS-related ethical dilemmas in the future.

When the potential future effects of CPS are examined, it becomes clear that many aspects of our personal and professional lives may be significantly impacted. Many legal difficulties, such as accountability, liability, data ownership, and privacy, are raised by the deployment of autonomous work robots connected to complex data environments. When constructing CPSs for activities involving humans, current safety laws must be updated to guarantee that no one is hurt and that the anticipated advantages outweigh any potential unintended consequences. These standalone policy briefs may be suitable for actual usage by the following congressional committees: Ethical issues and soft repercussions are translated into legal and regulatory considerations for cyber-physical systems. First, the STOA report might serve as a useful "tool" for the relevant committees as they formulate their

opinions on the draught DELVAUX report on robot civil legislation. If the report is approved, it is hoped that it will serve as the foundation for upcoming EU legislative efforts.

These systems, which combine computer, networking, and physical operations, have the potential to significantly increase productivity, security, and comfort. To make sure that these systems are created and utilized properly, CPS development and implementation also involve significant ethical issues, just like with any technological innovation. The possibility of greater surveillance and privacy invasion is one of the most urgent ethical issues concerning CPS. These technologies will probably gather enormous volumes of information about people and their behaviors as they spread throughout society. There are many potential uses for this knowledge, both good and bad. For instance, CPS data could be used to enhance municipal traffic flow, but it could also be used to track people's activities for sinister purposes. Strong privacy safeguards must be incorporated into the design of CPS in order to solve this issue, and there must be clear standards for the use of the data gathered by these systems. According to privacyinternational.org resource, massive surveillance involves the collection, processing, creation, analysis, use, or storage of data about a large number of individuals, whether or not they have been accused of wrongdoing. In democratic societies, comprehensive surveillance is neither essential nor proportional, thus creating challenges from a legal perspective. There are often less-invasive alternatives. We also question whether democratic societies can exist under constant scrutiny, especially if they do not. Mass surveillance creates the potential for unlimited state power and control over people through daily life surveillance. Fundamental values and principles of democratic societies aim to limit the information states know about their citizens to limit their power, but the assumption that all information helps counter hypothetical threats incompatible with mass surveillance undermines the separation of powers by giving the executive freedom of action without strict legislative or judicial regulation. Due to the fact that oversight powers are not granted in connection with every wrongdoing but collectively, mass oversight powers lack effective independent powers. In the eyes of the state, everyone is guilty until proven innocent, but this is incompatible with democratic ideals and principles. It fosters a climate of danger and mistrust. Finally, mass surveillance adversely affects other freedoms and rights. Unjustifiable invasions of privacy interfere with the enjoyment of other freedoms and often open floodgates to violations of other rights such as freedom of assembly, freedom of expression, and freedom of movement. Prohibition of discrimination and political participation.

The prospect of job displacement is another ethical problem associated with CPS. As these systems progress, they might be able to conduct jobs that formerly required human personnel. In some industries, especially those that entail manual labour or repetitive tasks, this could result in large employment losses. It has historically been the case that the development of new technologies has resulted in the creation of new jobs, but given the rapid improvements in CPS, it is uncertain whether this trend will continue. It is vital that governments and businesses invest in education and training programs to support workers' adaptation to the shifting labour market in order to lessen the possible negative effects of job displacement. Discussions regarding artificial intelligence's (AI) potential effects on the labour market have been spurred by the technology's rapid advancement. Concerns about intelligent machines replacing humans as workers grow as AI technology progresses. Automation of normal and repetitive tasks across numerous industries by AI has the potential to replace some job functions. Automation is more likely to occur with tasks that are simply specified, characterized, and conducted algorithmically. For instance, AI-powered robots on assembly lines can replace human labour in the manufacturing industry. Chatbots are getting better at answering simple questions in customer service. It is vital to understand that technical developments have traditionally changed the nature of employment rather than completely destroying occupations, even though job displacement due to AI is a threat. As regular jobs are automated, new career opportunities arise that call for aptitudes that are only possessed by people, including adaptability, emotional intelligence, creativity, and problem-solving. Additionally, AI can supplement human abilities, allowing employees to concentrate on more difficult jobs that call for complex decision-making and critical thinking. AI has the potential

to replace certain occupations while simultaneously creating new ones. AI engineers, data scientists, ethical experts, and policy analysts are just a few of the trained individuals needed for the creation, implementation, and maintenance of AI systems. AI can also stimulate economic growth by boosting productivity, encouraging innovation, and enabling companies to provide novel services and goods. Employment prospects in linked industries may result from this in turn. Retraining and upskilling programs are essential to reducing the possible negative effects of job relocation. Individuals can develop new talents that are in demand in the AI-driven job market by making investments in lifelong learning projects. Governments, educational institutions, and organizations must work together to offer easily accessible training programs at reasonable costs so that people can move into burgeoning professions. For managing the shifting work landscape, it will be crucial to place an emphasis on adaptation and lifelong learning. Even though losing a job may have economic repercussions, it's important to think about how it will affect society as a whole. To help displaced workers move on to new careers, there needs to be enough support mechanisms in place. Policies and rules should also address potential problems, including wage disparity, job polarization, and protecting employees' rights in the age of AI. It is essential to make sure that society as a whole receives the advantages of AI in an equitable manner.

Another moral issue that needs to be resolved is the possibility that CPS could be used as an instrument of social control. This technology has the potential to monitor and suppress opposition under an authoritarian system, enhancing the authority of a repressive administration. There is a chance that CPS will be employed to unfairly target particular groups or people according to their political opinions or other qualities, even in a democratic country. It is crucial that a solid legal framework be in place to safeguard people's rights and freedoms in order to prevent the exploitation of CPS for social control. The PiMind paper is an illustration of how CPS is used as a social control tool. Although it is currently feasible to make certain predictions about its implementation, Terziyan et al. (2018) believed that the digital twinning of human decision-making behavior required more advances in order to be validated. Pi-Mind Technology can be defined as a process where the world's most brilliant brains' decision-making processes are trademarked for use in high-tech machines. To enable the proper operation of the patented clones' decision-making behaviors, corporations must have incorporated sufficient technology. More than technology, it is essential that employees of the companies have a strong enough digital culture to inspire a desire for adaptability to new technologies. The advancement of technology and the use of CPSs in manufacturing facilities will significantly affect human employment. Companies will need to inspire employees and help them see the future in order to avoid issues like the inability to coordinate operations across various organizational divisions or a lack of employee enthusiasm and technical proficiency. In actuality, people will play a crucial role in the transition to the adoption of CPSs in businesses. In this situation, the development of decision-making clones acknowledges the existence of great minds that ensure the transformational process's success. The deployment of CPSs therefore necessitates the most skilled agents of the company because this process is dependent on the knowledge of individual employees. Additionally, it is asserted that this approach can capture cognitive elements of creative human decision-making based on individualized values and preferences. When applied to CPSs, this will have an effect since, despite the automatic decision-making approach, a human is still involved in the process. The so-called "Smart consultants," whose goal is to make recommendations to the human workers since they may not yet be able to replicate the human decision-making process, can be used to further integrate Pi-Mind technology into production. A decision maker needs to feel confident in the accuracy and completeness of the data in order to make a choice, and these "smart consultants" are equipped with the ability to gather data via the integrated CPS sensors in order to warn humans about potential problems. Pi-Mind agents can be structured as a single expert or as groups of autonomous Pi-Mind agents, forming a multi-agent system where the Pi-Mind robots communicate with one another. This interaction must be taken into account. Finally, the incorporation of legal considerations constitutes a crucial requirement for the

execution of this method to ensure that Pi-Mind agents' objectives and actions are consistent with and supportive of human values in all facets of their employment.

Accountability issues also pose serious ethical challenges in the context of CPSs, and as these systems become more autonomous, finding accountability for their activities may become more difficult. For example, if a self-driving car is involved in an accident, it can be difficult to determine whether the car's manufacturer, software developer, or owner is at fault. This lack of clarity can make it difficult for victims to seek financial compensation and for authorities to enforce safety regulations. According to Gruel & Stanford (2016) and Pernestl & Kristoffersson (2018), self-driving cars are predicted to fundamentally change the way we travel and use transportation. It will take a long time, require significant investments in infrastructure and vehicles, and require changes in behaviour and mindset. Full self-driving road vehicles are likely to be phased in over decades, perhaps only in limited locations such as parking lots and designated highways and highway lanes where speeds are minimized. This is a fundamental technical change. It takes a lot of effort to predict and evaluate all possible social changes caused by the introduction of the latest technology. As part of this effort, the ethical and political implications of the technology itself and possible deployment scenarios should be considered (Palm & Hansson, 2006). Much of the discussion about self-driving cars is about liability. Current tests on public roads always have a 'safety driver' or 'steward' at the wheel who is required to monitor traffic and take immediate control if necessary. Even without the advent of self-driving cars, traditional notions of who is responsible for what on the road have changed in recent decades. Historically, drivers and other road users have been primarily blamed (Melcher et al., 2015, p. 2868). Currently, our tolerance is very high when it comes to large differences in the hazards that different cars pose to other road users due to differences in equipment, driver skill, and actual attitude. To ensure a minimum level of technical safety, it is common in many countries to require monthly inspections of vehicles, including brake tests and other basic standard inspections. However, there are still significant differences between driver monitoring systems and anti-lock braking systems between car makes and models. Newer cars are generally held to higher standards than older ones. To our knowledge, there is no practice anywhere in the world to bring old vehicles up to the technical safety standards of new vehicles. Updating software in older vehicles can be a difficult problem, especially for vehicles beyond the manufacturer's lifetime (Smith, 2014).

4.2 Challenges against the development of cyber physical systems.

The Internet of Things, also known as IoT, has created this new ecosystem known as cyber-physical systems. Creation of new technologies and cutting-edge technical systems using computation, communication, and control in cyber-physical systems. A few decades ago, there was a lot of research on cyber-physical systems that society could not have foreseen. The development of this new ecosystem poses many risks and difficulties that raise questions about how human ethics will change. Therefore, this document also covers his CPS security issues. Security by design is one of the common problems in CPS. Most CPSSs are not designed with security in mind because they are not connected to any other network, such as the Internet. Most CPSS are not connected to any other network, so security is not a consideration in their design. Physical security is therefore paramount to ensuring personal safety. Physical security is the best way to keep people safe. Addressing both cyber and physical aspects of security requires CPS designers to redefine the way security is viewed. In the future, this could allow us to predict and stop cyberattacks that cause physical damage more accurately. We need to create a framework for both components of the cyber-physical solution that have been neglected so far. Inconsistent change is another difficulty facing CPS. There are many people working at CPS. This includes both those who work for them and those who produce, consume, own, and operate goods. Even if the roles and rights are different, it is important to manage them properly. Many people and various CPS departments have to deal with issues that cannot be overlooked during the transition. Community collaboration among her members involved in the CPS department will be very important at some point. Improvement methods include introducing new features, updating, or modifying

software, and upgrading hardware. Please keep in mind that unexpected changes to CPS security, such as new vulnerabilities, can compromise system security and cause serious national problems.

4.3 Smart grids challenges

Change management is a difficulty in the development of the smart grid. Change management in a smart grid is not any simpler than it is with ICS, but it is also not any more difficult. Smart grids are more sophisticated and involve more people, yet they struggle to adapt to change. As a result, change management is essential for a robust smart grid. Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) enables two-way communication in smart grids. AMI enables smart meters to communicate with utility providers near customers' houses, unlike the power grid, making it simpler for physical assailants to flee. In the smart grid, where there are more gadgets than ever before, it is getting harder to keep these devices secure. A strong access control system is necessary for smart grids because of their extensive reach and large investor base. It's crucial to keep an eye on and restrict any access that may be granted to network, data, or smart grid devices. Giving the individual or organization that is intended to assist enough power in an emergency is always the wisest course of action. Additionally, they are concerned about the use of their data. This has grown to be a significant issue for people as smart grids become more widespread. In addition to encrypting customer data, it's critical to provide anonymization procedures to stop hackers from deducing patterns from encrypted data to reveal sensitive information. We refer to this as "anonymization." Therefore, we must be sure that the systems we create can safely gather and encrypt data. There should not appear to be any trust placed in the delivered information and instructions in this situation. Alternately, new strategies to spot unauthorized false data and instructions must be developed. Due to the complexity of the smart grid, it may be challenging to employ specific algorithms that solely check for issues, making FDI attacks difficult to detect. Therefore, having elevated levels of security in a smart grid is beneficial. It's terrible at lower levels (since devices at lower levels have fewer capabilities). As a result, each level's required level of security might not be the same. To do this, numerous research teams must provide simple solutions. To keep data private and secure, encryption is crucial at all levels of the smart grid. To prevent any security breaches, do this.

4.4 Smart Vehicles challenges

There are contradictory security assumptions at the edge of integration when manufacturers integrate commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) and third-party modules into smart automobiles. According to the automakers, the COTS integration must be dependable, and other components must function well. It should guarantee that automakers do not compromise on safety in any way. If the Electronic Control Unit (ECU) of the gateway can be circumvented, then several attack methods, such as bypassing it and gaining access to constrained bandwidth, can be employed against it. Our cars can operate more efficiently by separating critical and non-critical ECUs, utilizing Ethernet or IP connections, and swapping out gateway ECUs for expert ECUs. Other partners in the automotive industry produce, buy, or import car spare parts and components. Both vendors and purchasers should focus more on security criteria, evaluation, and testing to make sure there are no security flaws or patches. Safety must be a consideration for manufacturers from the start of the design process. The CAN network is exposed due to the presumption that it is isolated. A new protocol that takes potential malevolent attackers into account is required. In the coming years, communication between vehicles (V2V) and infrastructure (V2I) will encounter a number of new security issues. It takes this danger to put an effective solution on hold and allow it to function.

4.5 Challenges in medical cyber-physical system.

Medical devices use technology to automate some functions, including hardware features such as security keys. However, given the importance of software development, it is generally accepted that

the Machine Copyright Protection Society's (MCPS) security cannot be guaranteed. Therefore, it is important to ensure that medical devices are certified, safe, accurate, efficient, and protected. Patient information provided during system contact can help diagnose illness earlier, alert emergency personnel, and provide a clearer picture of the patient's overall health. By enabling this device to be used to treat patients in the most effective manner, MCPS' analytical expertise can be leveraged to increase the flexibility of the device. In this way, the circuit should be closed quickly and safely. MCPS collects medical data and maintains the collected data, so security and privacy are paramount. Therefore, it is important to protect your data from being accessed or modified by anyone. As a result of such behaviour, patients may lose their privacy and be exposed to discrimination, abuse, and even physical violence from others. Additionally, most medical devices are designed to work for groups of people with similar medical conditions. Patients can react very differently to the same drug, so it can be very confusing and take a lot of time on MCPS. For example, most medical devices can simultaneously trigger an alarm when a potentially dangerous condition occurs. Medical devices can also cause false alarms. Parents do not do that. To effectively treat patients and collect information for electronic health records (EHRs), medical devices are now establishing robust network connections. In this case, studies should be conducted using flexible algorithms that can be adapted to the individual needs of patients. To reduce false alarms, it is planned to modify the alarm thresholds and display the patient's training history in her EHR. Future medical devices may integrate "smart alarm services" to reduce false alarms. Currently, it is the only company working on medical device integration and decentralized interoperability infrastructure, facilitating regulatory approval while reducing the benefits of device-to-device communication. The cornerstone of medical device interoperability is one of many open connectivity standards shared by MCPS. However, it would be more effective if this standard could be applied to a platform that is easy to build and use. To get the most out of their products and to ensure that they work together and integrate with each other, medical device manufacturers must follow a set of standards when developing their products.

5. CONCLUSION

In summary, wide embedded device deployment by CPS enables seamless real-world and virtual world integration, opening novel and intriguing business and research opportunities. It has a significant impact on our society and represents a brand-new paradigm for intelligent systems. CPS has been effectively used in several industries, including agriculture, manufacturing, transportation, healthcare, and more. However, the interaction between the dynamics of the cyber world, networking, and physical systems necessitates the use of fundamentally new advanced design technologies. Humans learn their values and expectations for moral behavior through experiences in their families, communities, schools, churches, and workplaces. Fundamental ethical principles have been upheld by a variety of societies and civilizations for centuries, and despite their strong foundation in human prosocial nature, social technology accelerates in a globally connected world. These changes are creating new situations such as: We can be more adaptive and future oriented. Smart CPHS will play a big role in driving these improvements. In order to fulfill our ethical obligations in many of our roles, we believe that the literature suggested in this article will serve as a basis for his discussion and development of CPHS ethics.

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